

RUBBER EXPORT PERFORMANCE IN INDIA

M. Prem* & S. Sowmiya**

* Assistant Professor, PG Department of Commerce with International Business,
Nallamuthu Gounder Mahalingam College, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** PG Department of Commerce with International Business, Nallamuthu Gounder
Maralinga College, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: M. Prem & S. Sowmiya, “Rubber Export Performance in India”, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Volume 7, Issue 1, Page Number 99-102, 2022.

Copy Right: © IJSRME, 2022 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Sensitization of natural rubber latex by addition of a small quantity of an anionic surfactant prior to the addition of a coacervant results in quick coagulation. The natural rubber prepared by the novel coagulation method shows improved raw rubber characteristics, better cure characteristics in gum and carbon black filled compounds and improved mechanical properties as compared to the conventionally coagulated natural rubber. Compounds based on dried master batches prepared by the incorporation of fluffy carbon black in different forms of soap sensitized natural rubber lattices such as fresh latex, preserved field latex, centrifuged latex and a blend of preserved field latex and skim latex show improved cure characteristics and vulcanizate properties as compared to an equivalent conventional dry rubber-fluffy carbon black based compound.

The fresh natural rubber latex based carbon black-silica master batch/ polybutadiene blend vulcanizates show superior mechanical and dynamic properties as compared to the equivalent compound vulcanizates prepared from the dry natural rubber-filler (conventional dry mix) / polybutadiene blends

Key Words: Carbon Black Master Batch, Coacervant, Fresh Natural Rubber Latex, Surfactant

Introduction:

The Rubber Board is a statutory body constituted by the Government of India, under the Rubber Act 1947, for the overall development of the rubber industry in the country. The importance of rubber production in India from strategic and security reasons had been realized by the government during the Second World War period. The rubber growers in India were encouraged to produce the maximum rubber required for the use during war. After the war, there were growing demands from the growers for setting up a permanent organization to look after the interests of the industry.

The Indian Rubber Industry plays a vital role in the Indian national economy. The rubber plantation sector in India produces over 630 hundred thousand tones of natural rubber and there is a projected production of more than one million tons in near future. This has helped in the radical and rapid growth of the Indian rubber industry. This prospect of growth is further enhanced by a boom in the vehicle industry, improved living standards of the people and rapid over-all industrialization.

Statement of the Problem:

Innovative and exploratory research calls for a statement of the problem of study on the industry considered for study. Although the district accounts for more than 90 per cent of latex production in the State of Tamil Nadu, the industries in operation are not producing useful rubber products such as automobile tyres, rubber bushes or numerous other industrial accessories as expected from such an industry. The trend in rubber production disproves the basic principles governing the localization of industries.

Unless efforts are made to overcome factors impeding the growth of such industries in the district, there is no gainsaying the fact that the growth of the rubber plantations would be in peril, in the days ahead. So this study would focus on this concern of industrial development and identify the factors responsible for non-proliferation of industries manufacturing rubber products. The study would also assess, at the same time, the potential for a steady and abundant supply of latex, which constitutes the major raw material for these products.

Objectives of Study:

The research aims at enriching the knowledge understanding role of export performance of cotton. The following are the objective of the study.

- To analyze the export performance of rubber products from India.
- To provide necessary suggestions based on the findings of the study.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of this project is involved the export performance of rubber products in Indian. The export performance of Indian rubber products is affected by the high competition. This study also gives growth rate and trend percentage of the export rubber products year wise and also country wise. The study provides suggestions to the rubber exporting industries to improve their performance

Research Methodology:

Secondary Data:

The secondary data is collected to supplement the primary data. The annual reports of sample units, Publications of Cotton products, in the website of Ministry of Commerce and Industries, Bulletins Working and Occasional Papers of EXIM Bank were used as important sources of secondary data for the stud.

Limitations of the Study:

- The analysis made only by considering 17 rubber and 10 major countries.
- Time constraint is one of the limitations.

Period of Study:

The research data is collected in 10 financial years. That years is 2010-2011 to 2019-2020

Review of Literature:

Stifle (1975) traced the efficiency of sheet rubber marketing system in Thailand in the frame work of the structure-conduct-performance model from the field of industrial organization. This analysis indicates that government can make competition more workable by measures to increase the producers' bargaining strength to increase the efficiency of the capital market, to encourage the standardization of product quality and by continuing to push feeder roads into remote producing areas to increase the size of effective market.

Chew (1984), measured the rate of technological change in Chinese rubber holdings. In this study he estimated the rate of technological change from a micro economic point of view. Acobb-douglas production was fitted to two sets of cross sectional data collected at different points of time. The study shows that the rate of technological progress in rubber smallholdings was the capita laugmentingty peat about 1.2 percent per year

George Tharian (1986) has made a study on the international commodity agreements, with special reference to natural rubber. He observed that there exists a higher degree of in stability in natural rubber prices in the international market and this exjoses the fragility of the frame work in which many of the commodity agreements are operating. Umadevi (1989) illustrate a statistical approach to examine the short run and long run response of rubber to price movements. The attempt in this study was to fit supply hnticlns for rubber with Indian data. She made findings that, the producers are influenced by the past six years' prices in their planting decision and that they positive l yres pond to price

Export of Rubber Product:

Table 1

* Values in USD

Year	Natrl Rubr Balath Guttapercha Etc And Smlr Natrl Gums In Prmry Frms (4001)	Growth Rate	The Synthetic Rubber And Factice Derived From Oils (4002)	Growth Rate	Reclaimed Rubber And Scrap of Rubber (4003)	Growth Rate	Waste Parings and Scrap of Rubber (4004)	Growth Rate	Cmpnded Ruber Unvulcnsd (4005)	Growth Rate
2010-11	122.87		38.47		52.92		6.99		15.54	
2011-12	94.13	35.11	58.26	51.44	68.01	28.51	5.36	-23.32	29.02	86.74
2012-13	127.18	-78.38	33.29	-42.86	74.08	8.93	0.97	-81.90	31.65	9.06
2013-14	27.49	-74.32	40.39	21.33	109.53	47.85	0.52	-46.39	22.66	-28.40
2014-15	7.06	729.18	62	53.50	82.6	-24.59	0.08	-84.62	84.94	274.85
2015-16	58.54	-35.69	69.28	11.74	71.76	-13.12	1.12	1300.00	15.07	-82.26
2016-17	37.65	-63.11	71.44	3.12	69.49	-3.16	0.92	-17.86	26.25	74.19
2017-18	13.89	-20.66	88.5	23.88	78.78	13.37	0.71	-22.83	38.25	45.71
2018-19	11.02	97.01	105.75	19.49	91.17	15.73	1.03	45.07	30.99	-18.98
2019-20	21.71	-100.00	107.07	1.25	79.76	-12.52	1.97	91.26	24.33	-21.49
AAGR	0.00		15.88		6.78		128.82		37.71	
CAGR	-0.64		-0.97		-0.94		-0.70		-0.95	

(Sources - EXIM data bank/ Ministry of commerce)

Interpretation:

The above table indicates that the rubber product exporting from India. That verities has contain many , and it classified for HS code basis , in this table the export of Natrl rubr balath guttapercha etc and smlr natrl gums in prmry frms (4001) has calculated the financial years from 2010-11 to 2019-2020. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 6 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Natrl rubr balath guttapercha etc and smlr natrl gums in prmry frms (4001) annual average growth rate is 0.00. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.64) because of decrease in year by year. The Synthetic rubber and factice derived form oils (4002) has calculated the financial years from 2010-11 to 2019-2020. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 1 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Synthetic rubber and factice derived form oils (4002) annual average growth rate is 15.88. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.94) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Reclaimed rubber and scrap of rubber (4003) has calculated the financial years from 2010-11 to 2019-2020. This growth rate was make a positive and negative results. Totally 4

years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Reclaimed rubber and scrap of rubber (4003) annual average growth rate is 6.78. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.94) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Waste parings and scrap of rubber (4004) has calculated the financial years from 2010-11 to 2019-2020. This growth rate was make a positive and negative results. Totally 6 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Waste parings and scrap of rubber annual average growth rate is 128.82. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.70) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Cmpnded ruber unvulcnsd (4005) has calculated the financial years from 2010-11 to 2019-2020 This growth rate was make a positive and negative results. Totally 4 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Cmpnded ruber unvulcnsd (4005) annual average growth rate is 37.71. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.95) because of decrease in year by year.

Export of Rubber Product:

Table 2

* Values in USD

Year	Other Form Articles of Unvulcanised (4006)	Growth Rate	Other Form Articles of Unvulcanised (4007)	Growth Rate	Plats, Shts, Strp, Rods and Profile Shapes (4008)	Growth Rate	Tubes, Pipes And Hoses of Vulcanized Rubber (4009)	Growth Rate	Cnyr Trnsmssn Blts/Bltnng of Vulcnsd Rubr (4010)	Growth Rate
2010-11	2.03		1.92		76		52.69		77.05	
2011-12	2.58	-39.04	2.49	29.69	96.27	21.06	72.46	37.52	111.27	44.41
2012-13	3.33	-25.43	3.22	29.32	82.6	-16.55	68.04	-6.10	121.11	8.84
2013-14	3.46	27.10	3.94	22.36	85.49	3.38	73.25	7.66	119.71	-1.16
2014-15	2.62	43.57	3.98	1.02	79.26	-7.86	90.89	24.08	115.02	-3.92
2015-16	2.41	-0.38	3.44	-13.57	67.21	-17.93	88.34	-2.81	103.2	-10.28
2016-17	2.63	-21.24	5.61	63.08	75.48	10.96	92.55	4.77	103.87	0.65
2017-18	3.06	-30.79	8.34	48.66	91.26	17.29	132.3	42.95	126.85	22.12
2018-19	3.8	-19.47	6.51	-21.94	108.06	15.55	166.87	26.13	143.87	13.42
2019-20	3.8	-19.47	6.95	6.76	102.83	-5.09	158.61	-4.95	140.05	-2.66
AAGR	-9.46		18.37		2.31		14.36		7.94	
CAGR	-0.96		-0.98		-0.94		-0.97		-0.95	

(Sources - EXIM data bank / Ministry of commerce)

Interpretation:

The above table indicates that the Rubber product exporting from India. That verities has contain many , and it classified for HS code basis , in this table the export of Other form articles of unvulcanised (4006) has calculated the financial years from 2010-2011 to 2019-2020. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 7 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Other form articles of unvulcanised (4006) annual average growth rate is -9.46. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.96) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Vulcanised rubber thread and ccord (4007) has calculated the financial years from 2010-2011 to 2019-2020. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 2 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Vulcanised rubber thread and cord (4007) annual average growth rate is 18.37. The compound growth rate will defines the positive value (-0.98) because of increase in year by year. The export of Plats, shts, strp, rods and profile shapes (4008) has calculated the financial years from 2010-11 to 2019-2020. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 4 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Plats, shts, strp, rods and profile shapes (4008) annual average growth rate is 2.31. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.094) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Tubes, pipes and hoses of vulcanized rubber (4009) has calculated the financial years from 2010-11 to 2019-2020. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 3 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Tubes, pipes and hoses of vulcanized rubber (4009) annual average growth rate is 14.36. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.97) because of decrease in year by year. The export of Cnyr trnsmssn blts/bltnng of vulcnsd rubr (4010) has calculated the financial years from 2010-11 to 2019-2020. This growth rate was making a positive and negative result. Totally 4 years of negative results are there and balance years are positive result. The Cnyr trnsmssn blts/bltnng of vulcnsd rubr (4010) annual average growth rate is 7.94. The compound growth rate will defines the negative value (-0.95) because of decrease in year by year.

Findings:

- In the case of the marketing of sheet and scrap, and in supplying planting materials the RPSs were found to be not so effective.
- Majority of the RPSs did not provide Community Smoke houses to the small rubber growers.

- In the case of the marketing of sheet and scrap, and in supplying planting materials the RPSs were found to be not so effective.
- Majority of the RPSs did not provide Community Smoke houses to the small rubber growers.

Suggestions:

- Newspaper reading habit should be developed among the rubber cultivators to know more about the day-to-day changes in cultivation, processing, marketing, cultivation techniques and so on.
- Awareness should be created among the cultivators about loan, and subsidies available to the cultivators.
- Proper training are to be provided to the cultivators during training about the use of modern IT based information tool such as Internet, e-mail for communication and Mobile Phone technology.
- The indigenous knowledge about rubber cultivation available among the co-cultivators must be properly recorded and digitalized by the Rubber Board for future use.

Conclusion:

India is the third largest producer, fourth largest consumer of natural rubber and fifth largest consumer of natural rubber and synthetic rubber together in the world. Besides, India is the world's largest manufacturer of reclaim rubber. In fact, India and China are the only two countries in the world which have the capacity to consume the entire indigenous production of natural rubber and thereby obviate the compulsion and over dependence on exports of surplus quantity of natural rubber. If the government take some precautionary measures and concrete steps to stabilize the rubber price both in the domestic and international markets, certainly the rubber cultivation can be more flourished.

References:

1. Bauer, P.T., (1948). "The Rubber Industry-A Study in Competition and Monopoly", London: Longman Green and Co.
2. Schidrowitz, P. and Dawson, T.B.,[Ed.], (1952). "History of the Rubber Industry", Cambridge, W. Heffer and Sons Ltd.
3. Andreuy Donnithrone, G.,(1958). "British Rubber Manufacturing", London: Gerald Deck worth and Co.
4. Stem, (1965)." Malayan Rubber Production, Inventory Holdings and the Elasticity of Export Supply", Southern economic Journal, vo1.31, No.4, April, pp: 314-323.
5. Dowling, (1977). "The Supply response of rubber in Thailand", Bangkok: Discussion Paper 58, Thamatsat University, Thailand